

An Open Source, Parallel, and Distributed Web-Based Probabilistic Risk Assessment Platform to Support Real Time Nuclear Power Plant Risk-Informed Operational Decisions

Milestone Report

Task 5: Applications to Multi-Hazard Real World PRA Models

Egemen M. Aras, Arjun Earthperson, Hasibul H. Rasheeq, S. Ted Wood (INL), Jordan T. Boyce (INL), Mihai A. Diaconeasa

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Executive Summary

This milestone report serves as a cornerstone demonstration of multi-hazard PRA modeling, leveraging OpenMHA for model development and solving the model using either SAPHIRE's graphical user interface or its external solver. The demonstration highlights the critical importance of both the modeling and solving phases in multi-hazard PRA. OpenMHA emerges as a promising tool for advanced model development, while the proposed model pre-processor in milestone report 2 shows significant potential for enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of model solving.

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Disclaimer

The content of this report is largely a combination of various project outcomes, including conference papers, a master's thesis, and a Ph.D. dissertation.

Outcomes of the Project

The project contributes to the research environment in various ways, and the outcomes are listed below for reference. In addition to the listed outcomes, two journal papers are ready for submission, and one report covering the SAPHIRE post-processing engine is under review. Furthermore, North Carolina State University and Idaho National Laboratory have established a highly efficient collaborative environment.

1.1 Conference Papers

1. Benchmark Study of XFTA and SCRAM Fault Tree Solvers Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models [1]
2. Methodology and Demonstration for Performance Analysis of a Probabilistic Risk Assessment Quantification Engine: SCRAM [2]
3. Method of Developing a SCRAM Parallel Engine for Efficient Quantification of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Models [3]
4. Introducing OpenPRA: A Web-Based Framework for Collaborative Probabilistic Risk Assessment [4]
5. Evaluating PRA Tools for Accurate and Efficient Quantifications: A Follow-up Benchmarking Study Including FTREX [5]
6. Introducing OpenPRA's Quantification Engine: Exploring Capabilities, Recognizing Limitations, and Charting the Path to Enhancement [6]
7. Enhancing the SAPHIRE Solve Engine: Initial Progress and Efforts [7]
8. Advancing SAPHIRE: Transitioning from Legacy to State-of-Art Excellence [8]
9. Towards a Deep-Learning Based Heuristic for Optimal Variable Ordering in Binary Decision Diagrams to Support Fault Tree Analysis [9]

1.2 Journal Papers

1. A Critical Look at the Need for Performing Multi-Hazard Probabilistic Risk Assessment for Nuclear Power Plants [10]

1.3 Reports

1. Refining Processing Engines from SAPHIRE: Initialization of Fault Tree/Event Tree Solver [11]

1.4 Master's Thesis

1. Benchmarking Study of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models: SAPHSOLVE, XFTA, and SCRAM [12]

1.5 Ph.D. Dissertation

1. Enhancement Methodology for Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools through Optimization and Parallel Computing [13]

Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY2

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....3

DISCLAIMER.....4

OUTCOMES OF THE PROJECT.....5

 1.1 Conference Papers.....5

 1.2 Journal Papers5

 1.3 Reports5

 1.4 Master's Thesis.....6

 1.5 Ph.D. Dissertation.....6

CONTENTS7

LIST OF FIGURES8

LIST OF TABLES.....9

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS10

1 APPLICATIONS TO MULTI-HAZARD REAL WORLD PROBABILISTIC RISK ASSESSMENT (PRA) MODELS.....11

 1.1 Overview of Report.....11

 1.2 Generic PWR Model with Multi-Hazard.....11

 1.2.1 Model Building Using OpenMHA11

 1.2.2 Model Quantification Using SAPHIRE12

 1.3 Conclusion and Alignment to Project Goals15

2 REFERENCES.....16

List of Figures

Figure 1. SAPHIRE linkage rule file for aftershock multi hazard PRA model.	12
Figure 2. Pseudocode for model quantification using SAPHIRE	13

List of Tables

Table 1. Generic PWR aftershock model solving time results for different truncation values.	14
Table 2. Generic PWR aftershock model results for different truncation values.	14

Acronyms and Abbreviations

GUI	Graphical User Interface
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MAR-D	Models and Results Database
PRA	Probabilistic Risk Assessment
SSC	Structures Systems and Components

1 Applications to Multi-Hazard Real World Probabilistic Risk Assessment (PRA) Models

1.1 Overview of Report

This report marks a significant milestone in the overall project. As a reminder, the project consists of six main tasks, which are outlined below. This milestone report presents the outcomes of the fourth task:

- Task 1: Literature review, benchmarking, and profiling of current PRA tools
- Task 2: Web-based PRA framework design and implementation
- Task 3: Testing and benchmarking for serial and parallel improvements
- Task 4: Applications to single hazard real-world PRA models
- Task 5: Applications to multi-hazard real-world PRA models
- Task 6: Verification and documentation

The remainder of the report is as follows: Section 1.2 delves into building and solving multi-hazard PRA model. Section 1.3 concludes the report with a summary of key findings.

1.2 Generic PWR Model with Multi-Hazard

A generic PWR model with multi-hazard capabilities is developed in two steps, building upon a single-hazard generic PWR model [14]. The initial step involves leveraging the single-hazard model, adding additional logic, and obtaining failure data for basic events using OpenMHA [15]. OpenMHA generates a Models and Results Database (MAR-D) [16] file containing all necessary information, including logic and failure probabilities, for use with SAPHIRE [17]. The second step involves importing the MAR-D file into SAPHIRE and solving the model. This can be done either through the graphical user interface (GUI) or by utilizing the SAPHIRE Solve Engine (SAPHSOLVE) [11] externally.

The process of building a multi-hazard PRA model using OpenMHA is summarized in Section 1.2.1, while the quantification of the multi-hazard model is detailed in Section 1.2.2.

1.2.1 Model Building Using OpenMHA

The OpenMHA framework is a cutting-edge tool designed to enhance multi-hazard PRA for nuclear power plants. It employs a comprehensive, scenario-based approach to modeling, incorporating spatial information, multi-hazard interactions, physical

simulations, and aging effects on structures, systems, and components (SSCs). By leveraging advanced simulation tools and probabilistic failure models, OpenMHA surpasses traditional conservative assumptions, enabling more realistic and accurate risk assessments.

OpenMHA integrates with an online database server (MongoDB Atlas [18]) to store essential data, including SSC failure modes, logic structures, and layout information. The framework connects to the server to interpret layout data and convert it into formats compatible with simulation tools.

The framework's core classes—**Fire**, **Flooding**, **Seismic**, and **Tsunami**—are interconnected, responsible for constructing scenario-specific fault tree logic and simulating hazard dynamics. While OpenMHA supports a wide range of multi-hazard scenarios, we will focus on the seismic class, demonstrating its ability to model not only the initial seismic event but also subsequent aftershocks.

1.2.2 Model Quantification Using SAPHIRE

The model-building step provides the foundation for model quantification by generating a MAR-D file. This file includes the updated fault tree logic and revised failure probabilities, accounting for subsequent aftershocks. Users are required to import the MAR-D file into SAPHIRE via its GUI, which enables detailed visualization of the multi-hazard PRA model.

The next step involves compiling a linkage rule file, as illustrated in Figure 1. Once this is complete, users have the option to solve the model either through the GUI or by invoking the SAPHIRE DLL, using a script by leveraging pseudocode shown in Figure 2.

```

1. IF SLOCA-EQ1-FT * LOOP-EQ1-FT THEN
2.   EVENTREE (EQK-BIN1) = FLAG (ETF-EQ1-SL);
3. ELSIF LLOCA-EQ1-FT * LOOP-EQ1-FT THEN
4.   EVENTREE (EQK-BIN1) = FLAG (ETF-EQ1-LL);
5. ELSE
6.   EVENTREE(EQK-BIN1) = FLAG(ETF-EQ1);
7. ENDIF
8. IF INIT (IE-EQ-BIN1) THEN
9.   EVENTREE (EQK-BIN1) = ENDSTATE (CD-EQ);
10. ENDIF
11.
12. IF INIT (IE-EQ-BIN1) THEN
13.   EVENTREE (EQK-BIN1) = FLAG(T-1);
14. ENDIF

```

Figure 1. SAPHIRE linkage rule file for aftershock multi hazard PRA model.

1. Import necessary libraries:
 - a. *os*: for file and directory operations
 - b. *threading*: for creating and managing threads
 - c. *ctypes*: to load and interact with the DLL
 - d. *time*: to measure solving times
2. Try to load the DLL:
 - a. If the DLL fails to load, print an error message and exit the script.
3. Define a function 'solve_json_file(input_file_path, output_directory)':
 - a. Generate the output file name by replacing the extension of the input file with '.JSCut'.
 - b. Measure the time taken to solve the JSON file using the SolveFromInput function from the DLL.
 - c. If there is an error during the solving process, print an error message.
4. Define a function 'solve_files_in_thread(files, input_directory, output_directory)':
 - a. For each file in the provided list of files, call the 'solve_json_file' function.
5. Define the 'main()' function:
 - a. Specify input and output directories.
 - b. List all JSON files in the input directory with the '.JSInp' extension.
 - c. Ensure the output directory exists; if it doesn't, create it.
6. Measure the time taken for serial processing:
 - a. For each JSON file in the list, call 'solve_json_file' to solve it serially.
 - b. Print the time taken for serial processing.
7. Measure the time taken for parallel processing:
 - a. Determine the number of CPU cores (threads).
 - b. Split the list of JSON files into chunks, one chunk per thread.
 - c. Create and start a thread for each chunk, calling 'solve_files_in_thread' in each thread.
 - d. Wait for all threads to complete.
 - e. Print the time taken for parallel processing.
8. Call the 'main()' function if the script is run directly.

Figure 2. Pseudocode for model quantification using SAPHIRE

Two different probability truncation values, 10^{-7} (E7) and 10^{-20} (E20), were used to solve the models, employing both the GUI and DLL solve methods. As shown in Table 1, the E7 truncation results reveal that solving the model through the GUI takes 643 seconds, whereas using the DLL method reduces this time to under 15 seconds. This demonstrates that SAPHIRE performs extensive pre-processing before solving the model, which significantly increases computation time. This finding highlights the need to improve pre-processing steps to speed up the overall calculation, as not all users utilize the DLL method. Furthermore, to use the DLL solve option, models must first be solved through the GUI to generate JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)-formatted input files—a process that is also computationally expensive and requires optimization.

The E20 results are particularly noteworthy. While GUI results could not be obtained even after waiting for over two hours, the input files generated during this attempt enabled the DLL solve method, which completed in just over three hours.

Table 1. Generic PWR aftershock model solving time results for different truncation values.

#	Input File / Truncation	Solve Time-GUI [sec]	Solve Time - DLL [sec]
1	EQK-BIN1 / E7	643.00	14.97
2	EQK-BIN1 / E20	N/A	11,784.49

Comparing the number and value of cut sets between E7 and E20, as shown in Table 2, we observe a significant increase in the number of cut sets with the finer truncation value, as expected. However, discrepancies in probability results were also observed. In some cases, these discrepancies are unacceptable, emphasizing the need for either exact solution methods or enhanced model pre-processors, as discussed in previous reports.

Table 2. Generic PWR aftershock model results for different truncation values.

#	Input File	Number of Sequences	Number of Cut Sets (E7)	Number of Cut Sets (E20)	Value (E7)	Value(E20)	Percentage Difference
1	EQK-BIN1_et_Grp-1	30	668	31,132,273	3.1090E-03	3.1656E-03	1.79%
2	EQK-BIN1_et_Grp-2	3	47	17,938	2.8278E-05	3.0606E-05	7.61%
3	EQK-BIN1_et_Grp-3	3	42	144,013	1.4515E-04	1.4668E-04	1.04%
4	EQK-BIN1_et_Grp-4	8	11	580,190	4.4697E-06	7.3165E-06	38.91%
5	EQK-BIN1_et_Grp-5	8	29	1,314,498	2.8961E-05	3.1139E-05	6.99%
6	EQK-BIN1_et_Grp-6	33	868	21,248,913	2.6158E-03	2.8147E-03	7.07%

1.3 Conclusion and Alignment to Project Goals

We approached multi-hazard PRA using two key pillars. The first pillar focuses on building the model, which involves leveraging single-hazard PRA models and expanding them using OpenMHA. OpenMHA provides a robust platform for analyzing complex hazard interactions and dependencies. It integrates MongoDB's flexible data management and powerful query capabilities to store and manage fault tree logic, spatial layouts, SSC failure modes and models, and hazard information. The output of OpenMHA is a MAR-D file that contains the necessary logic and failure probability information.

The second pillar involves importing the MAR-D file into SAPHIRE and solving the model, either through the GUI or by making a DLL call. Results indicate that while model-building is critical, solving the model is equally important. However, it has been observed that solving the model can take over three hours to approach exact results—results that remain unattainable using the current solution methods. To address this, we proposed a model pre-processing approach in previous milestone reports (Milestone Report 2), which shows promise in resolving probability discrepancies and improving efficiency.

As part of this project, various models have been developed and published. The demonstration of the multi-hazard PRA model serves as the final component of the project proposal.

2 References

- [1] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Benchmark Study of XFTA and SCRAM Fault Tree Solvers Using Synthetically Generated Fault Trees Models," in *Volume 9: Mechanics of Solids, Structures, and Fluids; Micro- and Nano-Systems Engineering and Packaging; Safety Engineering, Risk, and Reliability Analysis; Research Posters*, Columbus, Ohio, USA: American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Oct. 2022, p. V009T14A016. doi: 10.1115/IMECE2022-95783.
- [2] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Methodology and Demonstration for Performance Analysis of a Probabilistic Risk Assessment Quantification Engine: SCRAM," in *18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023)*, Knoxville, TN: American Nuclear Society, 2023, pp. 452–459.
- [3] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Method of Developing a SCRAM Parallel Engine for Efficient Quantification of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Models," in *18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023)*, Knoxville, TN: American Nuclear Society, 2023, pp. 134–140.
- [4] A. Earthperson, E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Introducing OpenPRA: A Web-Based Framework for Collaborative Probabilistic Risk Assessment," in *Proceedings of the ASME 2023*, New Orleans, Louisiana, USA, Oct. 2023.
- [5] A. Farag, S. Wood, A. Earthperson, E. Aras, J. Boyce, and M. Diaconeasa, "Evaluating PRA Tools for Accurate and Efficient Quantifications: A Follow-Up Benchmarking Study Including FTREX," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 573–582. doi: 10.13182/T130-43377.
- [6] E. Aras *et al.*, "Introducing OpenPRA's Quantification Engine: Exploring Capabilities, Recognizing Limitations, and Charting the Path to Enhancement," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 552–561. doi: 10.13182/T130-43362.
- [7] E. Aras, S. Wood, J. Boyce, A. Farag, and M. Diaconeasa, "Enhancing the SAPHIRE Solve Engine: Initial Progress and Efforts," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 542–551. doi: 10.13182/T130-43361.
- [8] S. Wood, J. Boyce, E. Aras, A. Farag, and M. Diaconeasa, "Advancing SAPHIRE: Transitioning from Legacy to State-of-Art Excellence," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 532–541. doi: 10.13182/T130-43357.
- [9] A. Earthperson, E. Aras, A. Farag, and M. Diaconeasa, "Towards a Deep-Learning based Heuristic for Optimal Variable Ordering in Binary Decision Diagrams to Support Fault Tree Analysis," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 400–409. doi: 10.13182/T130-43397.
- [10] E. M. Aras and M. A. Diaconeasa, "A Critical Look at the Need for Performing Multi-Hazard Probabilistic Risk Assessment for Nuclear Power Plants," *Eng*, vol. 2, pp. 454–467, 2021.

- [11] E. M. Aras, A. S. Amin Aly Farag, S. T. Wood, and J. T. Boyce, "Refining Processing Engines from SAPHIRE: Initialization of Fault Tree/Event Tree Solver," Idaho National Laboratory (INL), Idaho Falls, ID (United States), INL/RPT-23-75066-Rev000, Oct. 2023. doi: 10.2172/2203095.
- [12] A. S. Farag, "Benchmarking Study of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models: SAPHISOLVE, XFTA, and SCRAM," North Carolina State University, Raleigh, North Carolina, 2023.
- [13] E. M. Aras, "Enhancement Methodology for Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools through Diagnostics, Optimization, and Parallel Computing," Doctor of Philosophy, North Carolina State University, Raleigh, North Carolina, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://repository.lib.ncsu.edu/items/bb05f7f5-1cff-4beb-9312-331bc94b0b95>
- [14] C. Smith, "Generic Pressurized Water Reactor Model for SAPHIRE," INL/EXT-21-62553-Rev000, 1804754, Apr. 2021. doi: 10.2172/1804754.
- [15] A. Batikh and M. Diaconeasa, "OpenMHA: Open-Source Code for Creating Multi-Hazards Logic and Area PRA Models Considering Aging of SSCs," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 562–572. doi: 10.13182/T130-43381.
- [16] K. A. Branham-Haar, R. A. Dinneen, K. D. Russell, and N. L. Skinner, "Models and Results Database (MAR-D), Version 4. 0," NUREG/CR-5301, EGG--2627, 5299087, May 1992. doi: 10.2172/5299087.
- [17] "NUREG/CR-7039, Vol. 1, 'Systems Analysis Programs for Hands-on Integrated Reliability Evaluations (SAPHIRE) Version 8, Volume 1: Overview and Summary.,'" 2011. doi: 10.2172/130641.
- [18] "What is MongoDB Atlas? - MongoDB Atlas." Accessed: Dec. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mongodb.com/docs/atlas/>